

Polarographic Studies on Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II) Complexes of 3-Hydroxypyridine-2-Thiol

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Polarographic reduction of Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II) in presence of 3-hydroxypyridine-2-thiol has been studied. Diffusion controlled irreversible waves are obtained in all cases. Kinetic parameters, viz., transfer coefficient (α) and formal rate constant ($K_{f,h}^0$) have been evaluated. The order of stability of the complexes have been found to be $Cu^{2+} > Zn^{2+} > Ni^{2+}$.

SULPHUR atom either as a thiol, a thioether or a sulphide ion is an important ligand in certain biological systems. Polarographic investigations on the metal complexes of sulphur donor ligands, therefore, warrant attention. The present paper describes the results of polarographic investigations on Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II) complexes of 3-hydroxypyridine-2-thiol (HPT), a potential sulphur donor ligand. Kinetic parameters have been evaluated and order of the stability of the complexes has been discussed.

Polarographic studies on Nickel(II)¹⁻⁴, Copper(II)⁵⁻⁸ and Zinc(II)⁷⁻¹¹ complexes with Sulphur donor ligands have not received due attention.

Experimental

Polarograms were obtained on a manual polarograph recommended by Kolthoff. Current was measured on a galvanometer (General Electric Co., USA) which was standardised by passing a known current. The potential was measured by a Leeds Northrup students potentiometer standardised against a standard cadmium cell. All the potentials are expressed versus S.C.E. The capillary used had the following characteristics: $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.054$ $mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/2} h = 40$ cms and $t = 3.8$ seconds. All studies were made at room temperature ($30 \pm 0.1^\circ$).

Materials: Stock solutions of metal ions were prepared by dissolving A.R. grade salts in double distilled water. Solution of HPT (Fluka AG, Switzerland) was prepared in purified methanol due to its limited solubility in water.

Reagent grade chemicals were used for preparing buffers and electrolyte solution.

Technique: A series of solutions containing $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ metal ion, appropriate amounts of

supporting electrolyte, buffer, maximum suppressor (gelatin) and varying amounts of HPT were polarographed. The medium was 40% methanol. A fixed minimum distance was maintained between the electrodes and it was checked that the cell resistance did not exceed 1000 ohms. The solutions were previously deaerated by passing nitrogen, which was purified by bubbling through vanadous sulphate solution. A slow stream of nitrogen was maintained above the solution surface while recording polarograms.

Results and Discussions

Well defined single reduction waves are obtained in all cases. Studies with different heights of mercury column reveal constant value for $i_a/(h_{eff})^{1/2}$ indicating the diffusion controlled nature of the waves. Diffusion current, i_a , increases linearly with increase in metal ion concentration under similar experimental conditions. With increase in ligand concentration, $E_{1/2}$ shifts towards negative value indicating complex formation. The values of i_a fall in the range of two electron reduction. The plots of $-E_{de}$ vs. $\log(i/i_a - i)$ is linear for each system. Slopes of these lines are higher than the theoretical value of $2.303RT/nF$ indicating the irreversible nature of the waves. For the evaluation of the rate constant of the electrode reduction proper, the method developed by Koryta¹³⁻¹⁴, imposes an ambiguity in the gross assumptions that the increasing concentration of the ligand does not change the structure of electrode double layer. The heterogeneous rate constant for the overall cathodic process has been determined, therefore, by the modified method of Oldham and Parry¹².

According to these authors the equation for an irreversible diffusion controlled wave is

$$-E_{de} = -E_{1/2} + \frac{2.303 RT}{nF} \log \left[\frac{x(5.5-x)}{15(1-x)} \right] \dots (1)$$

where $x = \frac{i_E}{i_{lim}}$ (i_E = current at potential E) which is valid in the entire region $0 \leq x \leq 1$. From the plot of $-E_{d.e}$ vs. $\log \left[\frac{x(5.5-x)}{5(1-x)} \right]$, the values of $\frac{2.303 RT}{nF}$ and $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ can be evaluated from the slope and intercept respectively. Also for an irreversible wave the half-wave potential is related to the rate constant for the electrode reduction (at 30°) by the equation.

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = E_0 + \frac{2.303 RT}{nF} \log 0.89 k_{f,h}^0 \sqrt{\frac{t}{D}} \quad \dots (2)$$

where $k_{f,h}^0$ is the formal rate constant at an arbitrary chosen reference potential E_0 , ($E_0 = 0.0$ vs. NHE or -0.2412 vs. SCE) and D and t have their usual meaning. Values of kinetic parameters have been presented in Table 1.

TABLE-1 KINETIC PARAMETERS

Ligand concn. (mM)	$-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (volts vs. SCE)	αn	$D^{\frac{1}{2}} \times 10^3$ (cm.sec. ⁻²)	$k_{f,h}^0$ (cm.sec. ⁻¹)	$\alpha \Delta E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (volts)
Ni(II) - HPT, pH=9.7(NH ₄ Cl/NH ₄ OH Buffer) $\mu=0.1$ (KNO ₃)					
2.0	1.280	0.940	1.86	0.062×10^{-10}	0.085
4.0	1.300	0.935	1.84	0.037×10^{-10}	0.093
6.0	1.316	0.936	1.80	0.019×10^{-10}	0.101
8.0	1.324	0.935	1.80	0.015×10^{-10}	0.106
Cu(II) - HPT, pH=10.0(OH ⁻ /PO ₄ ³⁻ -Buffer), $\mu=0.1$ (KNO ₃)					
2.0	0.320	0.855	2.08	0.99×10^{-4}	0.137
4.0	0.340	0.850	2.06	0.52×10^{-4}	0.145
6.0	0.355	0.849	2.03	0.31×10^{-4}	0.151
8.0	0.362	0.847	2.01	0.25×10^{-4}	0.153
Zn(II) - HPT, pH=10.0 (OH ⁻ /PO ₄ ³⁻ -Buffer), $\mu=0.1$ (KCl)					
2.0	1.258	1.096	2.10	0.035×10^{-20}	0.115
4.0	1.273	1.086	2.08	0.030×10^{-20}	0.122
6.0	1.283	1.080	2.09	0.027×10^{-20}	0.126
8.0	1.286	1.074	2.04	0.019×10^{-20}	0.128

A perusal of results shows that irreversibility of the chelates is increasing in the order $Zn^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > Cu^{2+}$.

Since the increase in the concentration of the complexing agent does not cause any drastic change either in the shape or in the position of the reduction waves, it may be inferred that the mechanism of the electrode processes remains same throughout the concentration range and the main parameter which is influenced by the change in the composition of the solution is $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$. Since the stability of the complexes is reflected in the change in half-wave potential from simple metal ion to the complexed metal ion, a comparison of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ values may give an idea about the relative stabilities of the complexes of the metal ions under study. But in the case of

irreversible processes, the half-wave potential also depends upon α and, hence, the $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ values corresponding only to the same value of α may be compared. However, Vlček¹⁵ suggests that this difficulty may be overcome if the values of $\alpha E_{\frac{1}{2}}$, instead of those of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$, are used. The values of $\alpha \Delta E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ are listed in Table 1. The results show that the stability of the complexes follows the order, $Cu^{2+} > Zn^{2+} > Ni^{2+}$. This order is different from the common order of Irwing and Williams¹⁶ and Mellor and Malley¹⁷ only in that the positions of Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} are reversed. Murakami *et al*¹⁸ suggest that the greater stability of Zn^{2+} complexes may be due to the fact that besides $L \rightarrow M$ σ -bond there is some $M \rightarrow L$ π -interaction between the $d\pi$ orbitals of the metal ion and π -orbitals of the ligand molecule. Extent of such π -interaction with Zn^{2+} is greater than with Ni^{2+} .

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